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ENCOURAGING EFL LEARNERS TO IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH THE INTERACTIVE LISTEN-AND-ANSWER STORYTELLING

Ummatova Xusnida Abdujabbor qizi

*Uzbek State World Languages University. Foreign
language and literature (English). Masters degree. 2 course.*

Abstract: *The study investigates the effectiveness of listen and answer storytelling (adapted from A.J. Hoge’s Effortless English (2014) series) to enhance the speaking skills of Uzbek EFL learners. One-group pretest and posttest research design helped to compare before and after results of 20 pupils of 7th grade. The results indicated the mean EFL speaking skills score is 7.075 in the pretest and 8,485 in the post-test expressed a positive difference. P-value showed $<.001$, the difference was statistically significant. Cohen’s $d = 2.836$, the test distributes a small effect size. I conclude that storytelling is advantageous to develop EFL learners' speaking skills.*

Key words: *Speaking skills, listen and answer storytelling, CEFR speaking assessment criteria, Uzbek EFL learners.*

Introduction

The study aimed to explore the role of interactive teaching methods to inspire L2 learners to enhance speaking ability. Therefore, it focuses on investigating the effectiveness of listen and answer storytelling among Uzbek EFL learners. It is difficult for most students to have a real conversation in English, however, they have been learning English for years. There are several ways of improving speaking, one of them is storytelling.

When it comes to the purpose of storytelling is to help learners to speak confidently, socialize, increase creative thinking and develop morally. According to Mokhr, Kamarulzaman and Syed (2011) storytelling is the best way to develop other skills and it is very useful to improve second language learners’ communication skills. Mello (2001) states that “storytelling can improve the fluency and vocabulary”, can help students learn to listen (Mallen, 1992) as well as is helpful to grammatical rules (Sulaimani and Khandan, 2013).

First of all, the research will gather data by contrastive analyzing the works of scholars to define the point that has not been studied yet. Secondly, a class of school pupils are chosen as an experimental group and the listen and answer storytelling method

will be used for a specific time duration. According to quantitative data collected during the experiment, descriptive and initial statistics are demonstrated, then, the results are explained and discussed to conclude. The difference of the research from others, it is going to examine the productiveness of listen and answer type of storytelling method adapted by A. J. Hoge in his Effortless English series (2014) among Uzbek English learners. The study is going to address the following questions:

1. To what extent is listen-and-answer storytelling effective for EFL learners to improve speaking ability in Uzbek public school?

2. Are there any significant differences between the speaking skills of participants after the treatment in comparison to previous knowledge?

Background and Rationale of the Study

Language is means of communication that is gifted by God for the only human being. People use language to know and understand each other, furthermore, to express their thoughts, feeling, ideas. Speaking is an inseparable part of daily activities that are considered the main necessity for everyone. According to Thornbury (2005), speaking is a part of daily life that we take for granted. Therefore, speaking is one of the important skills in learning English as the second language among other skills (reading, listening, writing). Richard (2008) mentions that being good at speaking skills in English is a priority. Speaking covers five components (Harris 1969): pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency and comprehension.

In Uzbekistan, the government pays high attention to teaching English as a foreign language. So, it is the basic issue that to improve Uzbek learners speak skill acquisition by using different methods and techniques. One of them is telling stories. Asfandiyar (2007) defines storytelling is as the creative process that can activate unity of aspects such as intellectual, sensitivity, refinement, emotion and art. Nigora, J. (2020) explains that storytelling fasters creative thinking. It also helps students to express ideas in the format of beginning, development, and ending, including the characters and setting a story has to have.

Storytelling is an effective mean to create an English teaching environment that learners feel freer when they tell or retell different stories. If stories are unusual, exactly, include interesting facts, rarely used historical events, different real experiences, they (stories) will attract students' attention to keep their motivation to speak in classes. Learners have the concern to share typical less studied information with their peers because psychologically, everyone tends to be interested in abstract things. According to Ratih Inayah (2015) for teachers, creating a positive condition is important to make the

learners fun, interested, and motivated in learning English, moreover, to engage them actively participate in the learning process.

Methodology

One-group Pretest-posttest Research Design is chosen. This research design combines both posttest and pretest studies by carrying out a test on a single group before the treatment is administered and after the treatment is administered. The purpose of this strategy is to improve the EFL learners' speaking skills by using interactive listen-and-answer storytelling. Here, the interactive listen and answer storytelling is considered an independent variable which is the experimental treatment being exerted on the dependent variable that is the EFL learners' speaking skills. The level of measurement of variables is contentious because experimental research designs involve collecting quantitative data and performing statistical analysis on them during research.

Data collection plans

This study will be carried out in a remote area school in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. The whole class containing 20 learners (both female and male) of 7th grade will be selected as participants of the experiment. The interactive listen-and-answer storytelling method will experiment during a month including three lessons each week. The first and last lessons are for taking before and after tests, the other ten lessons are for working on experimental methods. Each participant will have a total of 15 minutes both answering the questions of the story and preparing picture storytelling. According to the instruction of the first task, researchers will tell only a sentence of the story, then ask questions based on the story, learners listen to the part of the story and give their answers, in this way four or five questions will be given to each learner. For example, a teacher tells *“Students, there was a monkey. Teacher asks: Was there a monkey? Student answers: “yes, there was a monkey”, the teacher asks: “Was there a monkey or a girl?”*. It is based on A.J Hoge storytelling method. In the second activity, the teacher will ask learners to tell their own stories using pictures. To check the students' knowledge and appropriateness of independent variables to their level assessment rubric is going to be utilized which is adapted from CEFR scoring criteria. It includes fluency and coherence, grammatical acceptability, ability to expand the idea, volume and pronunciation.

Data will be mainly collected orally under the control of researchers.

For the pretest and posttest, two activities will be prepared 1) show and tell 2) answer the question. In the first activity teacher will ask learners to bring one item, during testing teacher exchange all items, and participants will choose one and describe it such as: if the tested participant choose a 'book' among items, he/she will make a short speech about that thing. In the second activity, the tested learner will take their own and others

give questions about the item. Each participant will have 15 minutes for both activities. In short, these stories and tasks are created and designed to teach L2 learners to think in English, understand and speak.

Table 1. *Speaking assessment rubric (adapted from CEFR speaking assessment criteria).*

Componentstested	Weightageofmarks
Fluencyandcoherence	4 marks
Grammaticalacceptability	2 marks
Ability to expand the idea	1 mark
Volume	2 marks
Pronunciation	1 marks

2. Hypotheses

1. The null hypothesis (Ho) is that the method of listen and answer storytelling will be no effect in improving learners' speaking ability.

2. Alternative hypothesis (Ha) that the method of listen and answer storytelling will be productive in enhancing learners' speaking ability.

3.1 Scoring Procedures

The scoring speaking requires special assessment criteria which include some points. Speaking assessment rubric is adapted from 'CEFR assessment criteria' for our research, because of defining compatibility of storytelling for the level of learners. Mainly five components are tested, such as Fluency and coherence 4 points, grammatical acceptability 2 points, ability to expand the idea 1 point, volume 2 points and pronunciation 1 point. Participants can gather a totally of 10 points.

3.2 Reliability

From the instrument reliability, test retest reliability was used in order to calculate the result collected in a month time interval.

The rater reliability indicated high reliability because the maximum score is 9.6 over 9/10, (Table 3) it means that the results are reliable taking into consideration time interval and each suggestion given by the researcher separately relying on all components of the speaking assessment rubric (Table 1)

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

According to the method of the research, the instrument in collecting data for checking effectiveness of storytelling were "show and tell" and "answer the questions" activities. The researcher supported two types of tests: pre-test and post-test. The data were collected from class 7th in Uzbek public school.

The results are as follow:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	Pre-test_ speaking	post-test_speaking
Valid	20	20
Missing	0	0
Mean	7.075	8.485
Median	7.250	8.500
Mode	7.500	8.000
Std. Deviation	0.937	0.816
Minimum	5.000	6.800
Maximum	8.300	9.600

^a More than one mode exists, only the first is reported

Table 3. The score of Pre-test and Post-test in experimental class

	Participants	Pre- testresult	Post- testresult
	PP-1	7.5	8.6
	PP-2	5	7.5
	PP-3	7.5	9
	PP-4	8.2	9.5
	PP-5	7.5	8.5
	PP-6	6.3	8
	PP-7	6.3	8.4
	PP-8	7	9.3
	PP-9	8	9.5
0	PP-10	6.5	8
1	PP-11	7	8
2	PP-12	5.5	6.8
3	PP-13	7.7	8.5

4	PP-14	6	7
5	PP-15	8	8.8
6	PP16	8.2	9.6
7	PP-17	8.3	9
8	PP-18	7.5	9.4
9	PP-19	6.5	7.8
0	PP-20	7	8.5
	LOWEST SCORE	5	6.8
	HIGHT SCORE	8.3	9.6

4.2 Inferential Statistics

The researcher run the paired samples *t*-test because the pair samples *t*-test is used to measure one thing with two units. For example: pre-test and posttest for only one group.

Table 4. Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	f	p
Pre-test_ speaking	post-test_ speaking	-12.681	9	<.001

Note. Student's *t*-test.

While checking the assumption for paired sample *t*-test the researchers answered two questions:

- a) Is the DV continuous? b) Are the data normally distributed?

The dependent variable is continuous because it is the basis of gathering and demonstrating numerical data. Normality assumption run with the help of checking Histogram, or running Sapiro- Wilk’s test, and by checking normality in the JASP dataset. Here are the results:

Table 5. Assumption Checks

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)		W	p
Pre-test_ speaking	post-test speaking	0.942	0.265

Note. Significant results suggest a deviation from normality.

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	p	Cohen's d
post-test speaking	Pre-test_ speaking	2.6819	<.001	2.836

Note. Student's t-test.

Results and discussion

In order to determine whether using retelling stories has any effect on the subjects' speaking ability, after obtaining the scores of the pre-test and post-test, the mean and standard deviation of the scores were calculated. Then, in order to find out whether the differences between the groups were statistically significant, t-test analysis of the tests was run.

According to table 2, it shows that the mean L2 speaking skills score from the pre-test is 7.075 while the mean L2 speaking skills score from the post-test demonstrated 8.485 with slightly change. The means of the two tests say that there is a positive difference. The minimum score raised up from 5 to 6.8 comparing to the maximum ones express a rise from 8.3 to 9,6. Relying on the next table which tells about significance of research, it can be report that p-value shows <.001 it means it is less than .05 and the difference is statistically significant. According to the result of Cohen's d = 2.836, the test distributes small effect size.

When the two means are compared through the paired sample t-test, the result showed that the differences between two means was significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was accepted showing that there was a significance improvement in the speaking abilities of the EC students

taught using the storytelling technique compared to pre-test result with post-test after the treatment.

From those two of questions discussed above, it can be concluded that storytelling has found as a very useful method for improving students' speaking. It proved that it is helpful to convey words and images and it is accessible to all ages and abilities. As a learning tool, storytelling can encourage students to explore their unique expressiveness and can increase their imagination, new vocabulary and sentence structure and other skills. Therefore, this method could create a chance to develop not only EFL learner's speaking ability but other skills and capabilities also.

Conclusion, limitations and suggestions

Conclusion

Based on the result of the research it can be concluded that listen-and –answer storytelling technique works effectively in improving students speaking skills. The result of the research proved that the Uzbek public school EFL learners who were taught by using storytelling have better performance in speaking skills compared post-test results to pre-test. Moreover, according to the observation of the researcher, this method helped to develop learners' other language skills in process of practising with speaking simultaneously.

Limitation

If it is explained from different perspectives, there is at least a week side of each experiment, this research is not excepting of them. The researcher came across some difficulties with learners due to their learning style, although the scores showed high reliability. Storytelling was more easy and productive for audial learners, for the other two types it took extra time and explanation because one of them does best by seeing, the other does by touching.

Suggestions

Some suggestions for further research and for practical purposes are proposed to enhance and find better techniques for teaching-learning speaking for teachers, students and researchers. Teachers should use many and various techniques for teaching speaking since this can lead to innovative and creative thinking from the students and can make classes more lively and interesting. When choosing methods of teaching, it had better take into consideration the style of learning. In short, the teacher should be creative in making or searching for stories that can increase learners 'interest and enthusiasm.

Students should not be shy to practice speaking English and worry about making mistakes, being active and creative helps to enrich their speaking ability, besides that,

students should practice speaking inside and outside of the classroom at every chance they get.

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